

Rahu- Desire of being Immortal.

59 Comments / Blog / By Deepanshu Giri

Every one of us has many desires in life, and we work throughout our life to complete those; every graha in our chart comes with a desire- A Particular agenda, and this is what we try to complete in our lifespan, but this life is small to complete the agenda of all planets as at max a person can run 3-5 Mahadasas in their lifetime, Mahadasa decides the overall agenda of the life for next set of years and other planets either help or negate the agenda- Mahadasa is the primary direction explaining what your conditions will be, which part of the globe you will live in and what you will strive for in life until any Mahadasa is running.

Birth Dasa is a special dasa as this is the dasa that killed you in your last birth; a termination has happened in your last life due to this particular planet only, and now you are born with the same Mahadasa, completing the rest of karma, see birth and death as tiny dots in a big circle to give you transition to another circle.

Every scripture will explain that if you are born as a human, a significant amount of your punya is accumulated. You should be thankful for this birth, but let me come back to the desire of a Mahadasa

planet, as every planet has a specific agenda to be done if you ever wish to check past life check-in D-12, chart the position of the planet where you are born. You will know the deeper reason for your birth- I have written this in detail in the editorial of Lunar Astro October -2023 magazine with case studies.

I want to focus this article on the desire of Rahu. Every planet has a basic desire that planet wants to achieve through a superpower that has been granted to that particular planet, such as the desire of Jupiter to provide eternal happiness and raise your equivalent energy level to gods by giving you wisdom, the superpower of Jupiter is expansion and wisdom.

Similarly, Rahu desires to be immortal by using his superpower of being the mirror, A shape-shifter to look like someone else and be immortal, as this is how Rahu came into existence in the first place when nectar was being distributed and in this process, nectar was dropped in four places, Haridwar, Prayagraj, Triyambak & Ujjain, These four places have significant effect in the dasa of Rahu.

As in BPHS, it is mentioned that a person takes in the Ganga River during the dasa of Rahu because of chasing for the nectar drops dropped at these places. What I have personally observed with the Rahu dasa is that during this dasa, the native is chasing an illusion and keeps on running from pole to pole only to complete one desire, and that is to be immortal- Being immortal is not only the existence of physical body but a desire to be remembered and this is a basic human desire that there should be someone after them to remember them, To tell the tales of your greatness that once you lived on this earth and performed deeds, that is what we do during the Sharaddh paksha and amavas, To remember our ancestors and offer them food, clothes and other goods as a gratitude for all the good things our ancestors have done in life.

The greatest desire of Rahu is to become immortal and timeless so that you will be remembered in every era. The same is the desire of the Sun, but the difference between the two is that the Sun comes from the lineage and has fame by birth due to lineage and family someone is born into; this is an advantageous position. Rahu is the one who has risen from the extreme low like a phoenix rise from ashes against all odds, from down under the earth only by the blessings of ancestors; all the punya of several lineages gets manifested into a person who gets born with powerful Rahu, Rahu is the one and who never belonged to that class of royalty, never got equal status or respect as he is the odd one out, He is the brilliant outcast who is not accepted into the hall of fame.

Sun get fame and royalty quickly from day one and will be remembered in the afterlife due to their lineage. That is why all the kings had one strong desire: to get a Son who could carry their name forward while Rahu, on the other hand, would be remembered by many while living and after death, as Rahu came from a place where he stood against all odds, Arjuna got everything as a result of lineage while Karan even after all the obstacles managed to challenge the Arjun, You can't compare two warriors as one had all the advantages and another one had nothing.

A prominent feature of Rahu is to do good for the downtrodden society, which serves as a beautiful remedy for the Rahu as well, To help people overcome the difficulties you had faced while climbing

up. This is why the construction of rest houses, medical facilities or, like Karan -Donation to anyone in need every morning is one of the best remedies for Rahu; While bathing in river Ganga every time I have tried during the Rahu dasa and taken feedback from several people had resulted in headaches, body pains or something significant happened in next one week based on how powerful energy of Rahu you are carrying.

Why do you need to help the downtrodden outcasts of society during this dasa? Remember where you have come from. You have risen in life due to the energy of Rahu only, nothing else. This is why in the chart of politicians, Rahu has to be strong as the Sun is one big source of energy that has infinite power, which is passed through the nucleus DNA straight forward to you without any trouble as this is entitlement through the Sun. Still, the energy of Rahu is not passed on directly as an entitlement but via multiple people and generations helping you, rather than a core nucleus power is gathered via support of all the outcasts who have not got enough credit in the past, who possess you and consume all their desires through you and the moment the person who has got everything via the energy of Rahu says, Now its time for me to change and act like a Sun by normalising the energy, downfall starts as the power of Rahu lies in restlessness, hunger for win and use the energy of sixth house (Rog/Rin/Shatru). Imagine a politician starts thinking of a good at heart, and the system will throw him out as now he is useless to the system.

This is the official definition from the website of NASA for the black hole.

"A black hole is an extremely dense object in space from which no light can escape. While black holes are mysterious and exotic, they are also a key consequence of how gravity works: When a lot of mass gets compressed into a small enough space, the resulting object rips the very fabric of space and time, becoming what is called a singularity. A black hole's gravity is so powerful that it will be able to pull in nearby material and "eat" it."

What is written above is a definition of Rahu as the resulting object rips the fabric of space and time; you think deeper as all those who were oppressed by society, who were not accepted due to the lack of the authority backing them up, Who was threatening the society by not accepting the fate decided by the circumstances they were born in to. These people decided to run a parallel system of their own as the elite did not welcome them; always remember it is always the person who is in power who does not like anything to change in society as the current system and rules favour them- It is like a UN council. A few countries try to dictate their say on the whole world while countries like India, which has such a huge potential and growth, were made to sit on the side, and these people lecture us on climate change and poverty eradication to slow down the economic growth of rising India as growth and hunger of India is a threat for these nations, this has resulted in other groups such as BRICS, ASEAN and many other similar ones.

Astronomers have always wondered if there is a missing planet between Mars and Jupiter as the distance between these two planets is quite large; there are theories that a planet existed in this place that is the black hole at this place and in Vimshottari dasa sequence between Mars and Jupiter

there is a Rahu – the total distance between these two planets are 3.68 AU, Distance between Sun and Mars is 1.5AU and between Sun and Jupiter is 5.2AU and if you calculate distance between Sun and Rahu(Blackhole) should come around 2.3AU- 2.8 AU- You know what is the significance of these numbers are that you multiply these number by 18 years of Rahu dasa and you will get the age of Rahu which is 42-48 years of age.

This 2.3-2.8 is the span of the black hole when you calculate and go through the sheet provided by NASA- [Black Hole Math \(nasa.gov\)](https://www.nasa.gov/black-hole-math).

Don't forget that you have not got everything with a blessing from the Sun (Things which naturally get transferred via lineage); you have got these super ideas, brilliance and insights into this world because you had the energy of all these people combined, A strong Rahu, shows blessings of grandfather and your pitris as if Sun rules the sky, Rahu rules the Patal If you are able to break the generations of the cycle of poverty, bad luck and generational curses, keep giving back to Pataal.

Let us look at the History of what has happened to people who have donated to the cause and had a powerful Rahu in the chart. The donations will always help you keep extraordinarily rising in life. Pick up any chart of a person who has risen from rags to riches; the native will only be able to survive that phase if the native has given back to society. Otherwise, Rahu takes all back and gives it to someone else as remember the desire of Rahu- Your ancestors want to be remembered, The desire to live forever, and they can only do it through you; you don't get wealthy by your hard work but by blessings of ancestors when you fulfil their desire, Bill gates started charity in 1994 and in 1995 he was the richest man, Rahu in 6th in Scorpio- donation for medical causes and seed bank (Scorpio-6th house)

An Indian businessman donates 30% of his wealth to feed the poor. He started his career as a flea market vendor and now owns a big factory in the country, but his donations have not stopped yet; donations for a cause where Rahu is sitting in the name of ancestors are to be done to uplift the downtrodden and the moment this happens, helps comes from places you can't even imagine.

I hope this article has given you insights about Rahu and helped you overcome difficulties in your life.

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